

Solution of the system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations by using Cramer's rule

Yaser Ahmad Alhasan¹, Ashraf Abdallah Alnassan² and Asma Mohammed Alshallali³

¹Deanship of the Preparatory Year, Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University, KSA; y.alhasan@psau.edu.sa

²Deanship the Preparatory Year, Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University, Alkharj Saudi Arabia; a.alnassan@psau.edu.sa

³Deanship of the Preparatory Year, Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University, Alkharj, Saudi Arabia; a.allsallali@psau.edu.sa

*Corresponding author: y.alhasan@psau.edu.sa

Abstract: In this paper, we introduced Cramer's rule for solving a system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations. We defined the general form of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations and generalized this to system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations. In addition, we discussed several cases when solving a system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations. We also provided a set of examples to illustrate this.

Keywords: neutrosophic; Cramer; system of the equations; 2-refined; linear equations.

1. Introduction and Preliminaries

As a mathematical framework intended to manage several types of uncertainty, such as vagueness, ambiguity, imprecision, incompleteness, inconsistency, redundancy, and contradiction, Smarandache proposed Neutrosophic Logic in contrast to conventional logical systems.. This logic is part of a broader philosophical approach he called neutrosophy [4]. Within this framework, he defined the standard form of neutrosophic real numbers [3–5] and developed the foundation for neutrosophic statistics [5–6]. On the other hand, refined neutrosophic numbers studied by Smarandache [1]. Additional, advancements in neutrosophic differentiation and integration contributed by Y. Alhasan [2, 8–11, 13]. Agboola studied the refined neutrosophic algebraic structures [16]. In addition, Adeleke, Agboola and Smarandache introduced the refined neutrosophic rings I [17]. Moreover, the AH isometry was employed to investigate a range of mathematical structures, including conic sections, concepts in real analysis, and geometric surfaces [10, 14].

Alhasan presented study in types of system of the neutrosophic linear equations and Cramer's rule [15]. Motivated by this work, in this paper Solution of the system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations by using Cramer's rule studied.

Alhasan and Abdulfatah studied the division of refined neutrosophic number [18]:

$$\frac{a_1 + b_1I_1 + c_1I_2}{a_2 + b_2I_1 + c_2I_2} \equiv \frac{a_1}{a_2} + \left[\frac{a_2b_1 + b_1c_2 - a_1b_2 - b_2c_1}{(a_2 + c_2)(a_2 + b_2 + c_2)} \right] I_1 + \left[\frac{a_2c_1 - a_1c_2}{a_2(a_2 + c_2)} \right] I_2$$

Where: $a_2 \neq 0$, $a_2 \neq -c_2$ and $a_2 \neq -b_2 - c_2$

Mathematics is essential to many facets of life in the modern world, from the most basic everyday chores to the most intricate technical developments. Systems of linear equations stand out among its various subfields as a vital instrument for resolving practical issues. Linear equations enable us to model relationships and make rational judgments in a variety of contexts, including personal finance management, architectural design, scientific data analysis, and company operations optimization. Their broad range of applications in disciplines including computer science, engineering, economics, and logistics emphasizes their importance in both theoretical and real-world settings this is what prompted us to present this paper.

2. Main Discussion

2.1 The 2-refined neutrosophic linear equation

Definition 1

The 2-refined neutrosophic linear equation of n variables $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n$, is defined as:

$$(a_0 + b_0I_1 + c_0I_2)x_1 + (a_1 + b_1I_1 + c_1I_2)x_2 + \dots + (a_n + b_nI_1 + c_nI_2)x_n = d + eI_1 + fI_2$$

Where $a_0, a_1, \dots, a_n, b_0, b_1, \dots, b_n, c_0, c_1, \dots, c_n, d, e, f$ are real coefficients, and I_1, I_2 represent indeterminacy. We call $(a_0 + b_0I_1 + c_0I_2), (a_1 + b_1I_1 + c_1I_2) + \dots + (a_n + b_nI_1 + c_nI_2)$ 2-refined neutrosophic coefficients of the borders of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equation, and $d + eI_1 + fI_2$ constant neutrosophic border of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equation.

Remarks 1

The two-variable 2-refined neutrosophic linear equation defined as:

$$(a_0 + b_0I_1 + c_0I_2)x + (a_1 + b_1I_1 + c_1I_2)y = d + eI_1 + fI_2$$

Where $a_0, a_1, b_0, b_1, c_0, c_1, d, e, f$ are real coefficients, and I_1, I_2 represent indeterminacy.

Remarks 2

The three -variable 2-refined neutrosophic linear equation defined as:

$$(a_0 + b_0I_1 + c_0I_2)x + (a_1 + b_1I_1 + c_1I_2)y + (a_2 + b_2I_1 + c_2I_2)z = d + eI_1 + fI_2$$

Where $a_0, a_1, a_2, b_0, b_1, b_2, c_0, c_1, c_2, d, e, f$ are real coefficients, and I_1, I_2 represent indeterminacy.

Example 1

- $(-2 + 3I_1 + 8I_2)x + (5 + I_1 - 7I_2)y + (-3I_1 + I_2)z = 1 + I_1 - I_2$
- $(-8 - I_1 + I_2)x + (4 + 5I_2)y + (4 + 4I_1 + 2I_2)z + (-1 + I_1 + I_2)w = 1 - 7I_2$
- $(3 + I_1 + 5I_2)x + (10 + I_1 + 12I_2)y = 9 + 6I_1 - 2I_2$

Definition 2

Let the n-variable 2-refined neutrosophic linear equation

$$(a_0 + b_0I_1 + c_0I_2)x_1 + (a_1 + b_1I_1 + c_1I_2)x_2 + \dots + (a_n + b_nI_1 + c_nI_2)x_n = d + eI_1 + fI_2$$

Finding the values of the variables $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n$ that make its first term equal to its second term is solution of the n-variable 2-refined neutrosophic linear equation.

where $a_0, a_1, \dots, a_n, b_0, b_1, \dots, b_n, c_0, c_1, \dots, c_n, d, e, f$ are real coefficients.

Example 2

The equation: $(2 + I_1 + I_2)x + (4 - 2I_1 + I_2)y = 1 - I_1 + 2I_2$ accepts the solution

$$x = 1 + I_1 + I_2, \quad y = \frac{-1}{4} - \frac{41}{15}I_1 - \frac{7}{20}I_2$$

because:

$$\begin{aligned} L_1 &= (2 + I_1 + I_2)(1 + I_1 + I_2) + (4 - 2I_1 + I_2)\left(\frac{-1}{4} - \frac{41}{15}I_1 - \frac{7}{20}I_2\right) \\ &= 2 + 6I_1 + 4I_2 - 1 - 7I_1 - 2I_2 = 1 - I_1 + 2I_2 = L_2 \end{aligned}$$

2.2 Solution of the two-variable 2-refined neutrosophic linear equation

The two-variable 2-refined neutrosophic linear equation:

$$(a_0 + b_0I_1 + c_0I_2)x + (a_1 + b_1I_1 + c_1I_2)y = d + eI_1 + fI_2$$

has infinite number of solutions:

$$\begin{aligned} S &= \left\{ (x, y) \in R^2 \cup \{I_1, I_2\} : y \right. \\ &= -\left(\frac{a_0}{a_1} + \frac{a_1b_0 + b_0c_1 - a_0b_1 - b_1c_0}{(a_1 + b_1 + c_1)(a_1 + c_1)} I_1 + \frac{a_1c_0 - a_0c_1}{a_1(a_1 + c_1)} I_2 \right) x + \frac{d}{a_1} \\ &\left. + \frac{a_1e + ec_1 - db_1 - b_1f}{(a_1 + b_1 + c_1)(a_1 + c_1)} I_1 + \frac{a_1f - dc_1}{a_1(a_1 + c_1)} I_2 \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Where $a_0, a_1, b_0, b_1, c_0, c_1, d, e, f$ are real coefficients, and I_1, I_2 represent indeterminacy. $a_1 \neq 0$, $a_1 \neq -c_1$ and $b_1 \neq -a_1 - c_1$, by given a value for one of the two variables, we obtain a value for the other variable.

Example 3

Let's find the solution of the equation:

$$(-4 - 3I_1 - I_2)x + (-8 + 4I_1 + 2I_2)y = 5 - I_1 + I_2$$

$$y = \left(\frac{4 + 3I_1 + I_2}{-8 + 4I_1 + 2I_2} \right) x + \frac{5 - I_1 + I_2}{-8 + 4I_1 + 2I_2}$$

$$y = \left(\frac{-1}{2} - \frac{19}{6}I_1 - \frac{1}{3}I_2 \right) x - \frac{5}{8} - \frac{3}{2}I_1 - \frac{3}{8}I_2$$

Then:

$$S = \left\{ (x, y) \in R^2 \cup \{I_1, I_2\} : y = \left(\frac{-1}{2} - \frac{19}{6}I_1 - \frac{1}{3}I_2 \right) x - \frac{5}{8} - \frac{3}{2}I_1 - \frac{3}{8}I_2 \right\}$$

By given any value for x , we obtain a value of y .

Remarks 3

The general situation: solution of the n-variable 2-refined neutrosophic linear equation for the n-variable 2-refined neutrosophic linear equation:

$$(a_0 + b_0I_1 + c_0I_2)x_1 + (a_1 + b_1I_1 + c_1I_2)x_2 + \dots + (a_n + b_nI_1 + c_nI_2)x_n = d + eI_1 + fI_2$$

is infinite number of solutions, Where $a_0, a_1, \dots, a_n, b_0, b_1, \dots, b_n, c_0, c_1, \dots, c_n, d, e, f$ are real coefficients, and I_1, I_2 represent indeterminacy.

3. System of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations

It is a system of 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations that given by the form:

$$\begin{cases} (a_{11} + b_{11}I_1 + c_{11}I_2)x_1 + (a_{12} + b_{12}I_1 + c_{12}I_2)x_2 + \dots + (a_{1n} + b_{1n}I_1 + c_{1n}I_2)x_n = d_1 + e_1I_1 + f_1I_2 \\ (a_{21} + b_{21}I_1 + c_{21}I_2)x_1 + (a_{22} + b_{22}I_1 + c_{22}I_2)x_2 + \dots + (a_{2n} + b_{2n}I_1 + c_{2n}I_2)x_n = d_2 + e_2I_1 + f_2I_2 \\ \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots = \dots \\ \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots = \dots \\ (a_{m1} + b_{m1}I_1 + c_{11}I_2)x_1 + (a_{m2} + b_{m2}I_1 + c_{m2}I_2)x_2 + \dots + (a_{mn} + b_{mn}I_1 + c_{mn}I_2)x_n = d_m + e_mI_1 + f_mI_2 \end{cases}$$

Where:

$a_{ij}, b_{ij}, c_{ij}, d_j, e_j, f_j$ are real coefficients, $i = 1, \dots, n, j = 1, \dots, m$, and I_1, I_2 represent indeterminacy.

3.1 Solution the system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations

Solution of system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equation:

$$\begin{cases} (a_{11} + b_{11}I_1 + c_{11}I_2)x_1 + (a_{12} + b_{12}I_1 + c_{12}I_2)x_2 + \dots + (a_{1n} + b_{1n}I_1 + c_{1n}I_2)x_n = d_1 + e_1I_1 + f_1I_2 \\ (a_{21} + b_{21}I_1 + c_{21}I_2)x_1 + (a_{22} + b_{22}I_1 + c_{22}I_2)x_2 + \dots + (a_{2n} + b_{2n}I_1 + c_{2n}I_2)x_n = d_2 + e_2I_1 + f_2I_2 \\ \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots = \dots \\ \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots = \dots \\ (a_{m1} + b_{m1}I_1 + c_{11}I_2)x_1 + (a_{m2} + b_{m2}I_1 + c_{m2}I_2)x_2 + \dots + (a_{mn} + b_{mn}I_1 + c_{mn}I_2)x_n = d_m + e_mI_1 + f_mI_2 \end{cases}$$

Where:

$a_{ij}, b_{ij}, c_{ij}, d_j, e_j, f_j$ are real coefficients, $i = 1, \dots, n, j = 1, \dots, m$, and I_1, I_2 represent indeterminacy, is finding the values of the variables $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n$ that fulfill each of the system equations. We call this solution the system solution of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equation.

Remarks 4

We have three cases to solve the system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations:

- 1) The system may has unique solution
- 2) The system may be impossible to solve
- 3) The system may has infinite number of solutions

3.2 Cramer's rule to solve system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations

Let the system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations:

$$\begin{cases} (a_{11} + b_{11}I_1 + c_{11}I_2)x_1 + (a_{12} + b_{12}I_1 + c_{12}I_2)x_2 + \dots + (a_{1n} + b_{1n}I_1 + c_{1n}I_2)x_n = d_1 + e_1I_1 + f_1I_2 \\ (a_{21} + b_{21}I_1 + c_{21}I_2)x_1 + (a_{22} + b_{22}I_1 + c_{22}I_2)x_2 + \dots + (a_{2n} + b_{2n}I_1 + c_{2n}I_2)x_n = d_2 + e_2I_1 + f_2I_2 \\ \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots = \dots \\ \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots = \dots \\ (a_{n1} + b_{n1}I_1 + c_{n1}I_2)x_1 + (a_{n2} + b_{n2}I_1 + c_{n2}I_2)x_2 + \dots + (a_{nn} + b_{nn}I_1 + c_{nn}I_2)x_n = d_n + e_nI_1 + f_nI_2 \end{cases}$$

with the n variables and the n equations, let B the 2-refined neutrosophic coefficient matrix of the system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations, and suppose $\det(B) = a_0 + b_0I_1 + c_0I_2$, We distinguish the following cases:

- 1) If $\det(B) \neq 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$ and $a_0 \neq 0, a_0 \neq -b_0 - c_0, a_0 \neq -c_0$, then the system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations has unique solution given by:

$$x_i = \frac{\det(x_i)}{\det(B)} ; i = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

Where $\det(x_i)$ is the determinant produced by the determinant $\det(B)$ by replacing the column of constants with the i -order column.

- 2) If $a_0 = 0, a_0 = -b_0 - c_0, a_0 = -c_0$, then the system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations is impossible to solve.

- 3) If $\det(B) = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$, then we distinguish two cases:
- If one of the $\det(x_i) \neq 0; i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ then the system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations is impossible to solve.
 - If $\det(x_i) = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2; i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, then the system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations is impossible to solve or it have infinite number of solutions.

3.3 Solve the system of two 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations by two variables

$$\begin{aligned} (a_{11} + b_{11}I_1 + c_{11}I_2)x + (a_{12} + b_{12}I_1 + c_{12}I_2)y &= d_1 + e_1I_1 + f_1I_2 \\ (a_{21} + b_{21}I_1 + c_{21}I_2)x + (a_{22} + b_{22}I_1 + c_{22}I_2)y &= d_2 + e_2I_1 + f_2I_2 \end{aligned}$$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} + b_{11}I_1 + c_{11}I_2 & a_{12} + b_{12}I_1 + c_{12}I_2 \\ a_{21} + b_{21}I_1 + c_{21}I_2 & a_{22} + b_{22}I_1 + c_{22}I_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\det(B) = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} + b_{11}I_1 + c_{11}I_2 & a_{12} + b_{12}I_1 + c_{12}I_2 \\ a_{21} + b_{21}I_1 + c_{21}I_2 & a_{22} + b_{22}I_1 + c_{22}I_2 \end{vmatrix} = a_0 + b_0I_1 + c_0I_2$$

$$\det(x) = \begin{vmatrix} d_1 + e_1I_1 + f_1I_2 & a_{12} + b_{12}I_1 + c_{12}I_2 \\ d_2 + e_2I_1 + f_2I_2 & a_{22} + b_{22}I_1 + c_{22}I_2 \end{vmatrix} = a_0^x + b_0^xI_1 + c_0^xI_2$$

$$\det(y) = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} + b_{11}I_1 + c_{11}I_2 & d_1 + e_1I_1 + f_1I_2 \\ a_{21} + b_{21}I_1 + c_{21}I_2 & d_2 + e_2I_1 + f_2I_2 \end{vmatrix} = a_0^y + b_0^yI_1 + c_0^yI_2$$

We have the following cases:

- 1) If $\det(B) \neq 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$ and $a_0 \neq 0, a_0 \neq -b_0 - c_0, a_0 \neq -c_0$, then the system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations has unique solution given by:

$$x = \frac{\det(x)}{\det(B)}, \quad y = \frac{\det(y)}{\det(B)}$$

- 2) If one of the following conditions is satisfies, then the system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations is impossible to solve.
- i. $a_0 = 0$ and a_0^x, a_0^y are not all zero.
 - ii. $a_0 + c_0 = 0$ and $a_0^x + c_0^x, a_0^y + c_0^y$ are not all zero.
 - iii. $a_0 + b_0 + c_0 = 0$ and $a_0^x + b_0^x + c_0^x, a_0^y + b_0^y + c_0^y$ are not all zero.

- 3) If $\det(B) = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$, then we distinguish two cases:
- If one of $\det(x) \neq 0$ and $\det(y) \neq 0$, then the system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations is impossible to solve.
 - If $\det(x) = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2, \det(y) = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$, then the system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations have infinite number of solutions.

Example 4

Let's find solution of the following system:

$$\begin{aligned} (1 - 3I_1 - I_2)x - 2y &= I_1 - I_2 \\ (2 + 4I_1 + 3I_2)x + y &= 1 + 2I_2 \end{aligned}$$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} 1 - 3I_1 - I_2 & -2 \\ 2 + 4I_1 + 3I_2 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\det B = \begin{vmatrix} 1 - 3I_1 - I_2 & -2 \\ 2 + 4I_1 + 3I_2 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 5 + 5I_1 + 5I_2 \neq 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$$

hence the system has unique solution, is:

$$\det x = \begin{vmatrix} I_1 - I_2 & -2 \\ 1 + 2I_2 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 2 + I_1 + 3I_2, \quad \det y = \begin{vmatrix} 1 - 3I_1 - I_2 & I_1 - I_2 \\ 2 + 4I_1 + 3I_2 & 1 + 2I_2 \end{vmatrix} = 1 - 14I_1 + 4I_2$$

$$x = \frac{\det x}{\det B} = \frac{2 + I_1 + 3I_2}{5 + 5I_1 + 5I_2} = \frac{2}{5} - \frac{1}{10}I_1 + \frac{1}{10}I_2 \quad \text{and} \quad y = \frac{\det y}{\det B} = \frac{1 - 14I_1 + 4I_2}{5 + 5I_1 + 5I_2} = \frac{1}{5} - \frac{11}{10}I_1 + \frac{3}{10}I_2$$

$$(x, y) = \left(\frac{2}{5} - \frac{1}{10}I_1 + \frac{1}{10}I_2, \frac{1}{5} - \frac{11}{10}I_1 + \frac{3}{10}I_2 \right)$$

By substituting the value of x and y in the first equation, we find that the solution is satisfied, as follows:

$$L_1 = (1 - 3I_1 - I_2) \left(\frac{2}{5} - \frac{1}{10}I_1 + \frac{1}{10}I_2 \right) - 2 \left(\frac{1}{5} - \frac{11}{10}I_1 + \frac{3}{10}I_2 \right) = I_1 - I_2 = L_1$$

Example 5

Let's find solution of the following system:

$$(I_1 + 2I_2)x - 2y = 4I_1 - 2I_2$$

$$(5I_1 + I_2)x - 9I_2y = 5 + 7I_1 + 3I_2$$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} I_1 + 2I_2 & -2 \\ 5I_1 + I_2 & -9I_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\det B = \begin{vmatrix} I_1 + 2I_2 & -2 \\ 5I_1 + I_2 & -9I_2 \end{vmatrix} = -9I_1 - 18I_2 + 10I_1 + 2I_2 = 0 + I_1 - 16I_2$$

We can notice that $a_0 = 0$ and $a_0^x \neq 0$ so, the system is impossible to solve.

where:

$$\det x = \begin{vmatrix} 4I_1 - 2I_2 & -2 \\ 5 + 7I_1 + 3I_2 & -9I_2 \end{vmatrix} = 10 - 22I_1 + 24I_2$$

$$x = \frac{\det x}{\det B} = \frac{10 - 22I_1 + 24I_2}{0 + I_1 - 16I_2} \text{ (undefined)}$$

Example 6

Let's find solution of the following system:

$$(4 - I_1 + I_2)x - y = 4I_1 + 12I_2$$

$$(5 + 20I_1 - 20I_2)x + 3y = 13 - 8I_1 + 9I_2$$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} 4 - I_1 + I_2 & -1 \\ 5 + 20I_1 - 20I_2 & 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\det B = \begin{vmatrix} 4 - I_1 + I_2 & -1 \\ 5 + 7I_1 - 20I_2 & 3 \end{vmatrix} = 12 - 3I_1 + 3I_2 + 5 + 7I_1 - 20I_2 = 17 + 4I_1 - 17I_2 = a_0 + b_0I_1 + c_0I_2$$

$$\det x = \begin{vmatrix} 4I_1 + 12I_2 & -1 \\ 13 - 8I_1 + 9I_2 & 3 \end{vmatrix} = 12I_1 + 108I_2 - 13 + 8I_1 - 9I_2 = -13 + 20I_1 + 99I_2 = a_0^x + b_0^xI_1 + c_0^xI_2$$

Clearly that $a_0 = 17$ and $c_0 = -17 \Rightarrow a_0 + c_0 = 0$ and $a_0^x + c_0^x \neq 0$ so, the system is impossible to solve.

Example 7

Let's find solution of the following system:

$$\begin{aligned} (2 + I_1 + 3I_2)x + (3 + 2I_1 + I_2)y &= 1 + I_1 + I_2 \\ (4 + 2I_1 + 6I_2)x + (6 + 4I_1 + 2I_2)y &= 2 + 2I_1 + 2I_2 \end{aligned}$$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} 2 + I_1 + 3I_2 & 3 + 2I_1 + I_2 \\ 4 + 2I_1 + 6I_2 & 6 + 4I_1 + 2I_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\det B = \begin{vmatrix} 2 + I_1 + 3I_2 & 3 + 2I_1 + I_2 \\ 4 + 2I_1 + 6I_2 & 6 + 4I_1 + 2I_2 \end{vmatrix} = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$$

$$\det x = \begin{vmatrix} 1 + I_1 + I_2 & 3 + 2I_1 + I_2 \\ 2 + 2I_1 + 2I_2 & 6 + 4I_1 + 2I_2 \end{vmatrix} = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$$

$$\det y = \begin{vmatrix} 2 + I_1 + 3I_2 & 1 + I_1 + I_2 \\ 4 + 2I_1 + 6I_2 & 2 + 2I_1 + 2I_2 \end{vmatrix} = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$$

Clearly that $\det B = \det x = \det y = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$, so the system has infinite number of solutions defined as:

$$S = \left\{ (x, y) \in R^2 \cup \{I_1, I_2\} : y = \left(\frac{-2}{3} + \frac{5}{24}I_1 - \frac{7}{12}I_2 \right) x + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{6}I_2 \right\}$$

by given any value for x , we obtain a value of y .

3.4 Solve the system of three 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations by three variables

$$(a_{11} + b_{11}I_1 + c_{11}I_2)x + (a_{12} + b_{12}I_1 + c_{12}I_2)y + (a_{13} + b_{13}I_1 + c_{13}I_2)z = d_1 + e_1I_1 + f_1I_2 \quad (1)$$

$$(a_{21} + b_{21}I_1 + c_{21}I_2)x + (a_{22} + b_{22}I_1 + c_{22}I_2)y + (a_{23} + b_{23}I_1 + c_{23}I_2)z = d_2 + e_2I_1 + f_2I_2 \quad (2)$$

$$(a_{31} + b_{31}I_1 + c_{31}I_2)x + (a_{32} + b_{32}I_1 + c_{32}I_2)y + (a_{33} + b_{33}I_1 + c_{33}I_2)z = d_3 + e_3I_1 + f_3I_2 \quad (3)$$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} + b_{11}I_1 + c_{11}I_2 & a_{12} + b_{12}I_1 + c_{12}I_2 & a_{13} + b_{13}I_1 + c_{13}I_2 \\ a_{21} + b_{21}I_1 + c_{21}I_2 & a_{22} + b_{22}I_1 + c_{22}I_2 & a_{23} + b_{23}I_1 + c_{23}I_2 \\ a_{31} + b_{31}I_1 + c_{31}I_2 & a_{32} + b_{32}I_1 + c_{32}I_2 & a_{33} + b_{33}I_1 + c_{33}I_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\det B = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} + b_{11}I_1 + c_{11}I_2 & a_{12} + b_{12}I_1 + c_{12}I_2 & a_{13} + b_{13}I_1 + c_{13}I_2 \\ a_{21} + b_{21}I_1 + c_{21}I_2 & a_{22} + b_{22}I_1 + c_{22}I_2 & a_{23} + b_{23}I_1 + c_{23}I_2 \\ a_{31} + b_{31}I_1 + c_{31}I_2 & a_{32} + b_{32}I_1 + c_{32}I_2 & a_{33} + b_{33}I_1 + c_{33}I_2 \end{vmatrix} = a_0 + b_0I_1 + c_0I_2$$

$$\det x = \begin{vmatrix} d_1 + e_1I_1 + f_1I_2 & a_{12} + b_{12}I_1 + c_{12}I_2 & a_{13} + b_{13}I_1 + c_{13}I_2 \\ d_2 + e_2I_1 + f_2I_2 & a_{22} + b_{22}I_1 + c_{22}I_2 & a_{23} + b_{23}I_1 + c_{23}I_2 \\ d_3 + e_3I_1 + f_3I_2 & a_{32} + b_{32}I_1 + c_{32}I_2 & a_{33} + b_{33}I_1 + c_{33}I_2 \end{vmatrix} = a_0^x + b_0^xI_1 + c_0^xI_2$$

$$\det y = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} + b_{11}I_1 + c_{11}I_2 & d_1 + e_1I_1 + f_1I_2 & a_{13} + b_{13}I_1 + c_{13}I_2 \\ a_{21} + b_{21}I_1 + c_{21}I_2 & d_2 + e_2I_1 + f_2I_2 & a_{23} + b_{23}I_1 + c_{23}I_2 \\ a_{31} + b_{31}I_1 + c_{31}I_2 & d_3 + e_3I_1 + f_3I_2 & a_{33} + b_{33}I_1 + c_{33}I_2 \end{vmatrix} = a_0^y + b_0^yI_1 + c_0^yI_2$$

$$\det z = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} + b_{11}I_1 + c_{11}I_2 & a_{12} + b_{12}I_1 + c_{12}I_2 & d_1 + e_1I_1 + f_1I_2 \\ a_{21} + b_{21}I_1 + c_{21}I_2 & a_{22} + b_{22}I_1 + c_{22}I_2 & d_2 + e_2I_1 + f_2I_2 \\ a_{31} + b_{31}I_1 + c_{31}I_2 & a_{32} + b_{32}I_1 + c_{32}I_2 & d_3 + e_3I_1 + f_3I_2 \end{vmatrix} = a_0^z + b_0^zI_1 + c_0^zI_2$$

We have the following cases:

- 1) If $\det(B) \neq 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$ and $a_0 \neq 0, a_0 \neq -b_0 - c_0, a_0 \neq -c_0$, then the system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations has unique solution given by:

$$x = \frac{\det(x)}{\det(B)}, \quad y = \frac{\det(y)}{\det(B)}, \quad z = \frac{\det(z)}{\det(B)}$$

- 2) If one of the following conditions is satisfies, then the system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations is impossible to solve.

- i. $a_0 = 0$ and a_0^x, a_0^y, a_0^z are not all zero.
- ii. $a_0 + c_0 = 0$ and $a_0^x + c_0^x, a_0^y + c_0^y, a_0^z + c_0^z$ are not all zero.
- iii. $a_0 + b_0 + c_0 = 0$ and $a_0^x + b_0^x + c_0^x, a_0^y + b_0^y + c_0^y, a_0^z + b_0^z + c_0^z$ are not all zero.

- 3) If: $\det(B) = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$ and $\det(x) = \det(y) = \det(z) = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$, then we are searching for the solutions to two systems of equations, such as $\{(1), (2)\}$, then:

- The system $\{(1), (2), (3)\}$ is impossible to solve If $\{(1), (2)\}$ is impossible to solve.
- If $\{(1), (2)\}$ has infinite number of solutions from the form $x = g(z), y = h(z)$, (maybe $g(z)$ or $h(z)$ is constant), then we substitute in (3) to get:

$$0 \cdot z = \gamma; \quad \gamma \in R \cup \{I_1, I_2\}$$

According to the γ value, this equation can have an infinite number of solutions or impossible to solve.

Example 8

Let's find solution of the following system:

$$(1 + I_1)x + (1 + I_2)y + (1 + I_1 + I_2)z = 1 \quad (1)$$

$$(-1 - I_1)x + (1 + I_2)y + (1 + I_1 + I_2)z = 2 \quad (2)$$

$$(-2 - 2I_1)x + (2 + 2I_2)y + (2 + 2I_1 + 2I_2)z = 4 \quad (3)$$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} 1 + I_1 & 1 + I_2 & 1 + I_1 + I_2 \\ -1 - I_1 & 1 + I_2 & 1 + I_1 + I_2 \\ -2 - 2I_1 & 2 + 2I_2 & 2 + 2I_1 + 2I_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\det B = \begin{vmatrix} 1 + I_1 & 1 + I_2 & 1 + I_1 + I_2 \\ -1 - I_1 & 1 + I_2 & 1 + I_1 + I_2 \\ -2 - 2I_1 & 2 + 2I_2 & 2 + 2I_1 + 2I_2 \end{vmatrix} = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$$

$$\det x = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 1 + I_2 & 1 + I_1 + I_2 \\ 2 & 1 + I_2 & 1 + I_1 + I_2 \\ 4 & 2 + 2I_2 & 2 + 2I_1 + 2I_2 \end{vmatrix} = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$$

$$\det y = \begin{vmatrix} 1 + I_1 & 1 & 1 + I_1 + I_2 \\ -1 - I_1 & 2 & 1 + I_1 + I_2 \\ -2 - 2I_1 & 4 & 2 + 2I_1 + 2I_2 \end{vmatrix} = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$$

$$\det z = \begin{vmatrix} 1 + I_1 & 1 + I_2 & 1 \\ -1 - I_1 & 1 + I_2 & 2 \\ -2 - 2I_1 & 2 + 2I_2 & 4 \end{vmatrix} = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$$

As: $\det A = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2 = \det x = \det y = \det z = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$, so we are searching for a system solution $\{(1), (2)\}$, then:

$$x = \frac{-1}{2} + \frac{1}{4}I_1$$

$$y = (-1 - I_1)z + \frac{3}{2} - \frac{3}{4}I_2$$

By substitute in (3):

$$(-2 - 2I_1) \left(\frac{-1}{2} + \frac{1}{4}I_1 \right) + (2 + 2I_2) \left(\left(-1 - \frac{1}{2}I_1 \right) z + \frac{3}{2} - \frac{3}{4}I_2 \right) + (2 + 2I_1 + 2I_2)z = 4$$

$$(0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2)z = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$$

This equation has infinite number of solutions, so the system {(1), (2), (3)} has infinite number of solutions given by:

$$S = \left\{ (x, y, z) \in R^3 \cup \{I_1, I_2\} : x = \frac{-1}{2} + \frac{1}{4}I_1, y = (-1 - I_1)z + \frac{3}{2} - \frac{3}{4}I_2 \right\}$$

Or:

$$S = \left\{ \left(\frac{-1}{2} + \frac{1}{4}I_1, (-1 - I_1)z + \frac{3}{2} - \frac{3}{4}I_2, z \right) ; z \in R \cup \{I_1, I_2\} \right\}$$

Example 9

Let's find solution of the following system:

$$(1 + 3I_1 + I_2)x + (1 - I_1 + I_2)y + (2 + I_1 + I_2)z = 1 + I_1 + I_2$$

$$(-1 + I_1 + I_2)x + (1 + I_1 + 2I_2)y + (1 - I_1 + I_2)z = 2 - I_1 + I_2$$

$$(3 - I_1 + I_2)x + (4 - I_1 + I_2)y + (3 - 2I_1 + I_2)z = 1 - I_1 + 2I_2$$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} 1 + 3I_1 + I_2 & 1 - I_1 + I_2 & 2 + I_1 + I_2 \\ -1 + I_1 + I_2 & 1 + I_1 + 2I_2 & 1 - I_1 + I_2 \\ 3 - I_1 + I_2 & 4 - I_1 + I_2 & 3 - 2I_1 + I_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\det B = \begin{vmatrix} 1 + 3I_1 + I_2 & 1 - I_1 + I_2 & 2 + I_1 + I_2 \\ -1 + I_1 + I_2 & 1 + I_1 + 2I_2 & 1 - I_1 + I_2 \\ 3 - I_1 + I_2 & 4 - I_1 + I_2 & 3 - 2I_1 + I_2 \end{vmatrix} = -9 + 5I_1 - 7I_2$$

$$\det x = \begin{vmatrix} 1 + I_1 + I_2 & 1 - I_1 + I_2 & 2 + I_1 + I_2 \\ 2 - I_1 + I_2 & 1 + I_1 + 2I_2 & 1 - I_1 + I_2 \\ 1 - I_1 + 2I_2 & 4 - I_1 + I_2 & 3 - 2I_1 + I_2 \end{vmatrix} = 8 + 3I_1 - I_2$$

$$\det y = \begin{vmatrix} 1 + 3I_1 + I_2 & 1 + I_1 + I_2 & 2 + I_1 + I_2 \\ -1 + I_1 + I_2 & 2 - I_1 + I_2 & 1 - I_1 + I_2 \\ 3 - I_1 + I_2 & 1 - I_1 + 2I_2 & 3 - 2I_1 + I_2 \end{vmatrix} = -3 + 5I_1 - 5I_2$$

$$\det z = \begin{vmatrix} 1 + 3I_1 + I_2 & 1 - I_1 + I_2 & 1 + I_1 + I_2 \\ -1 + I_1 + I_2 & 1 + I_1 + 2I_2 & 2 - I_1 + I_2 \\ 3 - I_1 + I_2 & 4 - I_1 + I_2 & 1 - I_1 + 2I_2 \end{vmatrix} = -7 - 8I_1 - 5I_2$$

Then:

$$x = \frac{\det x}{\det B} = \frac{8 + 3I_1 - I_2}{-9 + 5I_1 - 7I_2} = \frac{-8}{9} - \frac{83}{176}I_1 + \frac{65}{144}I_2$$

$$y = \frac{\det y}{\det B} = \frac{-3 + 5I_1 - 5I_2}{-9 + 5I_1 - 7I_2} = \frac{1}{3} - \frac{5}{22}I_1 + \frac{1}{6}I_2$$

$$z = \frac{\det z}{\det B} = \frac{-7 - 8I_1 - 5I_2}{-9 + 5I_1 - 7I_2} = \frac{7}{9} + \frac{47}{44}I_1 - \frac{1}{36}I_2$$

hence, the system of equations has unique solution is:

$$(x, y, z) = \left(\frac{-8}{9} - \frac{83}{176}I_1 + \frac{65}{144}I_2, \frac{1}{3} - \frac{5}{22}I_1 + \frac{1}{6}I_2, \frac{7}{9} + \frac{47}{44}I_1 - \frac{1}{36}I_2 \right)$$

Verify the solution:

$$x + (1 + 2I_1 - I_2)y + 2I_1z = 0$$

$$I_1x + (1 + I_1 + I_2)y - I_2z = 0$$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} 3 + I_1 - 2I_2 & 1 - I_1 - I_2 & 3 + 2I_1 - I_2 \\ 1 & 1 + 2I_1 - I_2 & 2I_1 \\ I_1 & 1 + I_1 + I_2 & -I_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\det B = \begin{vmatrix} 3 + I_1 - 2I_2 & 1 - I_1 - I_2 & 3 + 2I_1 - I_2 \\ 1 & 1 + 2I_1 - I_2 & 2I_1 \\ I_1 & 1 + I_1 + I_2 & -I_2 \end{vmatrix} = 3 - 19I_1 + I_2$$

$$\det x = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 1 - I_1 - I_2 & 3 + 2I_1 - I_2 \\ 0 & 1 + 2I_1 - I_2 & 2I_1 \\ 0 & 1 + I_1 + I_2 & -I_2 \end{vmatrix} = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$$

$$\det y = \begin{vmatrix} 3 + I_1 - 2I_2 & 0 & 3 + 2I_1 - I_2 \\ I_2 & 0 & 2I_1 \\ I_1 & 0 & -I_2 \end{vmatrix} = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$$

$$\det z = \begin{vmatrix} 3 + I_1 - 2I_2 & 1 - I_1 - I_2 & 0 \\ I_2 & 1 + 2I_1 - I_2 & 0 \\ I_1 & 1 + I_1 + I_2 & 0 \end{vmatrix} = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$$

$$x = \frac{\det x}{\det B} = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$$

$$y = \frac{\det y}{\det B} = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$$

$$z = \frac{\det z}{\det B} = 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$$

hence, the system of equations has unique solution is: $(x, y, z) = (0,0,0)$

5. Conclusions

In this paper solution of system of the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations are discussed using Cramer’s rule. We have presented the conditions necessary to discuss the solutions of a system the 2-refined neutrosophic linear equations and we concluded that the system could have a unique solution, an infinite number of solutions, or be unsolvable.

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